

ISic1122

Dedication to 'Homonoia' (concord)

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8782

Physical Description

A small rectangular block of limestone, seemingly intact left, right and below, but damaged upper right

Dimensions

Height 23 cm

Width 41 cm

Depth 14 cm

Layout

single line of Greek letters across the middle of the stone

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Neatly incised letters without serifs: omicron is small and mid-line; mu has vertical first and last strokes, mid-strokes only descend halfway; nu has short diagonal and right vertical; alpha is broad with broken bar; sigma is incomplete but may have slightly open top and bottom strokes

Letter heights:

Line 1: 20-56 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ὁμολογίας

2. [---]

Apparatus

Traces of a second line, as read by Manni Piraino, are not obvious in the available photograph

Translation (en)

Of concord

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492735

EDR 140952

EDCS 39102278

PHI 140606

PHI 175605

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1122. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351565>

Photo R. Henzel, courtesy Palermo Museo Archeologico Regionale "A.Salinas"